

KitNewCare

Sustainable Care, Lasting Impact

KitNewCare, funded by the EU, pioneers innovations shaping the future of a more sustainable European healthcare.

The project empowers healthcare professionals with novel tools and knowledge, transforming kidney care and elevating patient health outcomes.

www.kitnewcare.eu

Join the Healthcare Revolution

Contact us at
info@kitnewcare.eu

Technological Innovations

Water Treatment

Reusing reverse osmosis reject water

Energy Efficiency

Solar-assisted dialysis

Waste Reduction

Minimising biohazardous waste

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